

June 12-15, 2022,
Novi Sad, Serbia

Living with **Risks:** Sharing the Good Practice

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

PUBLISHER

**UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD - FACULTY OF TECHNICAL SCIENCES
21000, Novi Sad, Dositej Obradovic Square 6, Serbia**

ORGANIZER:

- **The Society for Risk Analysis – Europe (SRA-E)**
- **University of Novi Sad - Faculty of Technical Sciences,
21000, Novi Sad, Dositej Obradovic Square 6, Serbia**

EDITORS

**Mirjana Laban,
Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia**
**Ljiljana Popović,
Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia**

TECHNICAL EDITOR

**Ljiljana Popović,
Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia**

Published in Novi Sad, June 2022
ISBN 978-86-6022-440-0

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE:

Rui Gaspar, president, Catholic University of Portugal, Portugal

Mirjana Laban, vice president, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Marja Ylönen, University of Stavanger, Norway

Frederic Boudier, University of Stavanger, Norway

Jamie Wardman, University of Nottingham, UK

Nicola Paltrinieri, Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway

Anna Olofsson, Mid Sweden University, Sweden

Kalliopi Sapountzaki, Harokopio University, Greece

Angela Bearth, ETH Zurich, Switzerland

Linda Makovicka Osvaldova, University of Žilina, Slovakia

Miroslava Vandalickova, University of Žilina, Slovakia

Jasmina Gačić, University of Belgrade, Serbia

Miloš Knežević, University of Montenegro, Montenegro

Vlatko Šešov, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia

Meri Cvetkovska, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia

Elona Pojani, University of Tirana, Albania

Perseta Grabova, University of Tirana, Albania

Zvezdan Karadžin, University of Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Edisa Nukić, University of Tuzla, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Gordana Broćeta, University of Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Ljiljana Popović, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Đorđe Ćosić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Srđan Popov, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Vlastimir Radonjanin, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Mirjana Malešev, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Igor Džolev, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Slobodan Kolaković, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Marko Marković, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Marija Jevtić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Ana Perišić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Tanja Vranić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Miroslav Miškić, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE:

Mirjana Laban, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences (Conference chair)

Ljiljana Popović, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Đorđe Ćosić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Srđan Popov, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Tanja Vranić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Senka Bajić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Slobodan Šupić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Suzana Draganić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Marko Vuković, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Cveta Lazić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

**Sandra Nedeljković, Government of the Republic of Serbia, Public Investment
Management Office**

Sanja Mrkšić Kovačević, University of Stavanger, Norway

IT SUPPORT:

Ines Perišić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

Rade Lučić, University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences

**All of papers in this Proceedings are reviewed under control of Scientific
Committee of 30th Annual Conference of Society for Risk Analysis – Europe:
Living with Risks – Sharing the Good Practice**

Society for Risk Analysis – Europe and Disaster Risk Management Centre, Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, organize 30th Annual Conference with the general subject “Living with Risks – Sharing the Good Practice”.

The scientist and risk professionals from all areas were invited to share their knowledge and experience of applied risk analysis and science, including risk assessment, risk characterization, risk perception, risk communication, risk management, risk governance and policy, relating to risks which are of concern to individuals, organizations in the public and private sector, or to society at local, regional, national, or global levels.

This conference, as well as the previous ones, contribute from all fields dealing with risk: Environment, Disaster Risk Reduction, Fire Safety, Health and Safety at Work, Urban Safety and Security, Insurance and Finance, Project Management Risks, Cyber Security, Terrorism and all other risk topics from practice.

Members of the International Scientific Committee actively participated in the preparation of the conference, both as reviewers and authors. Annual meetings/conferences are an opportunity for risk analysts to come together to discuss issues, problems, goals and future research questions. New areas for risk analysis are emerging and new disciplines are contributing to the ongoing debate about risk analysis in its various facets.

This year the authors from 27 countries participate in the conference, and the Book of abstracts contain 116 abstracts. The editors are sincerely grateful to all the authors for the contribution to this event.

Editors

Isolation measures and state of emergency - importance for mental health (example from Serbia)

Nada Tatalović

Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Slavica Dabižljević

Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Marija Jevtić

Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

Mirjana Laban

Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia

Abstract

Mental perception of declaring a state of emergency and introducing measures of restricted movement by population largely depended on circumstances in which the respondents found themselves - such as housing, number and age of household members, type of job or profession. Restrictions imposed numerous challenges, insecurities and fears. Limited conditions of movement brought changes in the ways of communication and informing.

The paper was created as a result of research in the subject of Mental Health and Psychosocial Support in Crisis, in PhD studies in the field of Disaster Risk Management and Fire safety, Faculty of Technical Sciences in Novi Sad. 765 respondents participated in the survey. Methodology was based on voluntary participation, an anonymous questionnaire and appropriate statistical processing. Respondents were asked to complete a questionnaire via email, Viber or WhatsApp.

The largest number of respondents, about 52% lived in households with three or more members, and 9% of respondents lived alone. The dominant fear that arose among the respondents was concern for their loved ones, in about 70% of the total number of respondents. 27% of respondents during the observed period were afraid of going to the store or using public transport. Over 22% of respondents were afraid of being infected and 16% of respondents were afraid of being admitted to a covid hospital.

The communication was significantly changed in the circumstances of the applied measures. It took place through channels that were available in conditions of limited movement. The highest percentage of respondents used mobile phones (91%), 72% used applications for communication on mobile phones (Viber, WhatsApp), 64% of respondents used social networks, while chat applications (such as Skype, Zoom) used about 37% of respondents.

The way of informing was most often limited to household sources - TV and Internet. About 55% of respondents used conferences of crisis headquarters as a source, about 45% of respondents were informed through informative programs on television, 39% via Internet and about 38% of respondents followed website and announcements of the Ministry of Health.

Almost two years of pandemic crisis passed with the application of various measures depending on current epidemiological situation, and the challenges of combating fear and uncertainty among the population (overcoming infectious diseases) are still present today. The results of the research indicate the importance of further monitoring of this topic and the importance of preserving mental health in future crises.

Key words: risk fall, bed, pressure integrate sensor, predictive model